

Figure 1

Figure 2

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Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

fig. S1. Loss of eEF-2K results in CD8⁺ T cell exhaustion. WT and eEF-2K KO CD8⁺ T cells were activated using anti-CD3/CD28 antibodies for six days. **(A)** Flow cytometric analysis was performed to assess expression of PD-1 and CD62L. The graphical representation of dot-plot analysis in triplicates was shown. **(B)** Graphical representation of flow cytometric assay for CD27 and CD28 on days 1 and 3.

A.

B.

fig. S2. Loss of eEF-2K differentially regulate protein expression. (A) LC-MS/MS Proteomics analysis of WT and eEF-2K KO CD8⁺ T cells was represented by Venn-diagram showing differentially expressed proteins. (B) Comparative heatmap analysis of senescence and apoptosis markers of WT and eEF-2K KO CD8⁺ T cells derived from the proteomics spectral analysis.

fig. S3. Upregulation of PD-1 and Tim-3 in eEF-2K KO CD8⁺ T cells can be abrogated by rapamycin (mTOR-i). Flow cytometric analysis of PD-1 and Tim-3 expression in WT CD8⁺ T cells, eEF-2K KO CD8⁺ T cells and eEF-2K KO CD8⁺ T cells treated with rapamycin (mTOR-i). Data shown are the graphical representation of the data of 3 independent experiments.

A.

fig. S4. Loss of eEF-2K compromises the cytotoxicity of eEF-2KO CD8⁺ T cells. Control MC38 cells or the MC32 CEA Ag-expressing cells were co-cultured with WT or eEF-2K KO CD8⁺ T cells, and then their cytotoxicity was assessed. (A) Representative dot-plots obtained from flow cytometric analysis followed by graphical representation of the dot-plots. (B) Graphical representation of LDH release assay of MC32-CEA colon cancer cells co-cultured with WT or eEF-2K KO CD8⁺ T cells. (C) The bright field images of the B16-OVA cells co-cultured with control (No OT-I CD8⁺ T cells), WT (non-transduced OT-I CD8⁺ T cells) or eEF-2K-overexpressing OT-I CD8⁺ T cells.

fig. S5. Expression of costimulatory and exhaustion markers by the CEA-specific CAR- CD8⁺ T cells with or without eEF-2K. On day 28 after adoptive transfer, the WT or eEF-2K KO Thy1.2 CD8⁺ T cells (**Figure 6**) were analyzed for the expression of various costimulatory and exhaustion markers, using flow cytometry for graphical representations of expression derived from flow cytometric dot plots. (**A**) CD27. (**B**) CD28. (**C**) TIM3. (**D**) PD-1. The intracellular cytokine expression was also assessed from the WT or eEF-2K KO Thy1.2 CD8⁺ T cells after re-stimulating the cells ex-vivo with anti-CD3/CD28 antibodies. (**E**) IL-2. (**F**) IL-1α. (**G**) IL-4. (**H**) IFN-γ. (**I**) TNF-α. (**J**) Graphical representation of 5 independent fields of tumor infiltrating lymphocytes as observed in confocal microscopy depicted in **Fig. 6G**. Graphical data shown are mean ± SD from values derived from 3 different wells of 3 independent experiments. **p* < 0.05; ***p* < 0.01; ****p* < 0.005 *****p* < 0.0001.

A

B

